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ULTRASOUND GUIDED POPLITEAL NERVE BLOCK FOR VARIOUS ANKLE & FOOT SURGERIES

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Abstract

Background: Ankle & foot surgeries are very common surgeries in various age groups like young & geriatric as well as in patients with comorbidities. Popliteal nerve block is one of multimodal Anaesthesia & analgesia for same. we have used ultrasound guided block to prevent complications & precise volume at a site for improving Characteristics of block.

Aims of study:

To study the technique of giving popliteal nerve blocks with ultrasonographic guidance and evaluate it in terms of:

No of attempts, Time required for sensory and motor blockade, Quality of Intra operative analgesia, Duration for post-operative analgesia, Supplementation required in form of sedo analgesia/general anaesthesia & Complications encountered.

Methods: We performed ultrasonography guided popliteal nerve block in 60 adult patients of **ASA grade I/II/III** undergoing foot and ankle surgeries. The **volume of drug** used was **20ml** consisting of Lignocaine (1.5%) 10ml and Bupivacaine (0.5%) 10ml; **Results:**

The **mean time taken** to conduct the block was 4.3 ± 1.4 mins. The mean time taken for **sensory onset** was 3.8 ± 1.1 mins. The mean time taken for **motor onset** was 7.0 ± 1.4 mins. The mean time taken for **completing the surgery** was 39.2 ± 5.0 mins. The mean time taken for **complete motor regression** was 143.8 ± 13.5 mins. The mean time taken for **complete sensory regression** was 184.8 ± 16.8 mins. The patients **first complained of pain** at the mean time of 239 ± 22.4 mins.

The patients have **stable haemodynamic parameters: pulse rate, SBP, DBP** throughout the operation. **Failure of block** was seen in 4 patients where supplementation in the form of Injection Midazolam 1mg IV and Injection Fentanyl 50microgm IV was given in 2 patients and general anaesthesia was given in 2 patients. No other neurological complications were noticed in our study.

Conclusion: ultrasound guided Popliteal nerve block is safe & effective block for various ankle & foot surgeries.

Key words: Ankle & Foot surgeries, popliteal nerve block, Ultrasound guidance

INTRODUCTION

The majority of the sensory and motor innervation of the foot and lower leg is provided by the sciatic nerve. There is a smaller sensory-only component, provided by saphenous nerve, which itself is derived from the femoral nerve. Blockage of the sciatic nerve in the popliteal fossa is a common technique to provide regional anaesthesia and analgesia for foot and ankle surgery.

Various authors have studied ultrasound guided regional Anaesthesia techniques for ankle & foot surgeries. (2-8) Regional anaesthesia at the knee has been resurrected from obscurity, evaluated and analyzed in the literature during the past fifteen years.^{19, 36, 39} In general, regional blockade is ideal for ambulatory type surgery. Advantages include perioperative analgesia and the avoidance of systemic complications like nausea and vomiting, early discharge from post anaesthesia care unit and decreased opioid consumption perioperatively.¹⁸

There are several approaches to administer the popliteal sciatic nerve block. Commonly, a posterior approach is employed with the patient positioned prone. Alternatively, the lateral approach can be used with the patient in the supine position. The medial approach has been described in the literature, although it is utilized less frequently.¹⁶

The use of ultrasound allows direct real time visualization of the deposition of the local anaesthetic (LA) and so can improve the chance of successful nerve blockade.⁴⁵ Ultrasound also allowed dose reduction of the local anaesthetic (LA).²¹ It reduces the block performance time, reduces the number of needles passes and shortens the block onset time.

Ultrasound guidance will allow the anaesthetist to detect this division and modify the procedure such that both branches are effectively blocked as well as the posterior femoral cutaneous nerve, a branch of the sacral plexus innervating posterolateral thigh segments that cannot be blocked by conventional means because it is separated from the sciatic nerve at the level of the proximal thigh²⁴.

METHODS

The present study was conducted in 60 patients who underwent elective foot and ankle surgeries having ASA grades I, II and III. **Pre-anaesthetic assessment:** all patients were thoroughly assessed preoperatively, informed consent taken & VAS was explained in detail.

✦ Inclusion criteria:

- A. Patients with ASA grades I, II, III.
- B. Patients willing to enroll in the study.
- C. Surgeries on foot or ankle only.
- D. Patients with age equal to or above 18.

✦ Exclusion criteria:

- Patients who do not give consent.
- A. Patients with known bleeding disorders.
 - B. ASA grade more than III.
 - C. Pregnant women.
 - D. Patients who were having septicemia.
 - E. Patients with local site infections.
 - F. Mentally retarded patients

Preparation:

An intravenous line was secured with an 18G/20G intravenous cannula. Noninvasive blood pressure monitoring and ECG monitoring was started. Pulse oximetry monitoring was also started. Pre procedure and intraoperative vitals were noted.

Drugs prepared: injection Lignocaine 1.5% 10 ml and injection Bupivacaine 0.5% 10 ml.

Anaesthesia workstation prepared for cardiopulmonary resuscitation.

Ultrasound machine and its probe properly cleaned and aseptically prepared for the procedure.

Position: patient was positioned prone with head turned to the opposite side and hands kept by the side.

Landmarks: anatomical landmarks were identified and marked with a skin marker which included the course of the semitendinosus tendon and the biceps femoris tendon. The mid popliteal crease was identified and marked.

Procedure: Block was performed by consultant anaesthetists who have given at least 30 blocks ultrasound guided, & having ethical clearance & license to use ultrasound machine for perpetual nerve block to avoid any medico-legal issues.

After preparing the parts with iodine, spirit and normal saline solutions, proper draping was done and a high frequency (5-12 Hz) ultrasound probe was placed transversely at the mid popliteal crease. After localizing the popliteal artery, it was moved proximally to locate the sciatic nerve at or prior to its bifurcation into the tibial and peroneal branches. A 23G spinal needle was inserted using out of the plane approach. The needle tip was advanced until it reached very close to the nerve visualized as a bright dot. Once placement was confirmed by questioning the patient verbally regarding the presence of par anaesthesia in the foot and ankle region, injection Lignocaine 1.5% 10 ml and injection Bupivacaine 0.5% 10 ml was injected. Sensory block was assessed by Hollman scale⁴⁰ and motor block was assessed by the ability to plantar flex the ankle (using the Hollman scale)⁴⁰. Monitoring was carried out and all the data was entered into a spreadsheet program. Time taken for sensory and motor blockade to recede completely was noted and also was the time taken till the onset of pain postoperatively. Below are reference diagrams illustrating the same.

Figure 4

Figure 5: BF: biceps femoris. ST, SM: semimembranosus, semitendinosus.

Figure 6

Figure 7: Figure shows the sciatic nerve (arrowheads) in the popliteal fossa before it divides.

Figure 8. Injection of anaesthetic agent was confirmed by visualization.

Figure 9 Stars showing deposition of local anaesthetic agents.

Following parameters were noted:

- I. Time taken for the procedure
- II. No of attempts needs to localize the sciatic nerve
- III. Onset and duration of sensory blockade. iv. Onset and duration of motor blockade.
- IV. Need of supplementary sedation/general anaesthesia.
- V. Onset of pain for the first-time post procedure.

DEFINITIONS OF PARAMETERS:

Time taken for the procedure: interval between preparation of the local part and administration of the full dose of the local anaesthetic.

Number of attempts: the number of times the skin has to be punctured with the Quincke spinal needle to localize the sciatic nerve and inject the full dose of the local anaesthetic agents.

Onset of sensory blockade: interval between injection of the full dose of local anaesthetic agents to the complete loss of pinprick sensation over the ankle and the foot.

Onset of motor blockade: interval between injection of full dose of local anaesthetic agents to the complete inability to plantar flex the ankle.

Duration of sensory blockade: interval between onset of sensory block to the first-time pin prick sensations are felt again by the patient on periodic checking.

Duration of motor block: interval between onset of motor block to the time when the patient is able to plantar flex the ankle.

Failure of block: inadequate analgesia, sensory blockade or motor blockade even after 30 minutes of injection of local anaesthetic solution. It was managed by giving **supplementation** in the form of anxiolytics like Injection Midazolam 1 mg IV and Injection Fentanyl 50microgm IV in anxious patients or with general anaesthesia.

Onset of pain: interval between onset of sensory block and the first time when the patient complains of pain.

▪ **Evaluation of sensory block (Hollman scale)⁴⁰:**

1. normal sensation of pin prick
2. pin prick felt as sharp pointed but weaker compared with same area in the upper limb
3. pin prick perceived as touch with blunt object
4. complete loss of pin prick sensation

▪ **Evaluation of motor block (Hollman scale)⁴⁰:**

1. normal muscle function
2. slight weakness in function
3. very weak muscular function
4. complete loss of function.

After completion of surgery, patient was shifted to post-operative ward and watched for regression of sensory and motor blockade periodically. Vitals were also recorded. When VAS was greater than 4 rescue analgesia in the form of Injection Tramadol 50mg IV given. Time to rescue analgesia was noted. Patients were further managed conventionally according to the department protocol.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All the data was entered in a spreadsheet program and statistical analysis were done using Microsoft excel version 2019 16.0.6742.2048 software.

RESULTS

Our study consisted of **60** patients, with ages ranging from **18 to 77 years** and weight ranging from **40 to 89 kilograms** as illustrated below. Mean age of patients was 52.8 yrs.

GRAPH 1 SHOWING AGE IN YEARS

Mean weight was 63.3 ± 10.3 kg

Our study comprised of patients having ASA grades I, II and III. There were 16 females and 44 males.

TABLE 1 SHOWING ASA GRADE OF PATIENTS

	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
ASA I	17	3	20
ASA II	20	11	31
ASA III	7	2	9
TOTAL	44	16	60

As illustrated below in Graph 3, 4, 5 the hemodynamic parameters of patients remained stable and apart from the rise in pulse, SBP and DBP at 5 minutes, which may be attributable to the anxiety response caused by the needle prick during the procedure, they remained close to baseline values throughout the operation. After the operation, in postoperative ward, as block effect wore off the patients' haemodynamic parameters were raised slightly above the baseline.

GRAPH 3 SHOWING PULSE VARIATION.

GRAPH 4 SHOWING SYSTOLIC BP VARIATION

GRAPH 5 SHOWING DIASTOLIC BP VARIATION.

TABLE 2 SHOWING TIME TAKEN TO EXECUTE THE BLOCK(MINS)

TIME TAKEN (MINS)	PATIENTS
3	21
4	20
5	9
6	4
7	4

8	2
MEAN	4.3
SD	1.4

The mean time taken to conduct the block was 4.3 ± 1.4 minutes

MEAN TIME FOR SENSORY ONSET WAS 3.7+/-1.1 MIN

GRAPH 6 SHOWING SENSORY ONSET VARIATION

MEAN TIME TO MOTOR ONSET WAS 7+/-1.4 MINS

GRAPH 7 SHOWING MOTOR ONSET VARIATION

The mean time taken for the sensory onset was 3.8 ± 1.1 mins while that for the motor onset was 7.0 ± 1.4 mins as shown

The mean time taken for completion of the operations was 39.2 ± 5.0 mins.

GRAPH 8 SHOWING COMPLETE MOTOR REGRESSION VARIATION

GRAPH 9 SHOWING COMPLETE SENSORY REGRESSION VARIATION

The mean time taken for complete motor regression was 143.8 ± 13.5 mins while for sensory regression was 184.8 ± 16.8 mins.

Time to first rescue analgesia was 239 ± 22.4 mins

COMPLICATIONS:

Failure of blockage and supplementation required

Four cases can be considered a failure. Because two patients were managed with sedation and analgesia by Injection Midazolam 1mg IV and Injection Fentanyl 50microgm IV. Two patients required general anaesthesia.

Haemodynamic complications:

Haemodynamic parameters were near baseline and normal **Neurological complications:**

No neurological sequelae was observed in any case in my study.

DISCUSSION

The popliteal nerve block is a form of regional anaesthesia utilized for a variety of foot and ankle conditions. This form of anaesthesia has become a popular technique to decrease postoperative pain, decrease narcotic use, and increase patient satisfaction. This is evident by an increase in published techniques within foot and ankle literature in the 21st century.¹⁰ Furthermore, a publication by Hege Wald et al. has demonstrated that not only is the popliteal block highly efficacious, but can also be executed by the novice foot and ankle surgeon. Popliteal blocks can potentially be utilized as the sole source of anaesthesia for foot and ankle surgery. This can be beneficial in medically compromised patients. Profound analgesia during both the operative and postoperative time periods and the avoidance of systemic complications such as nausea and vomiting are also potential benefits of the popliteal nerve block. Other advantages include earlier discharge from the post-anaesthesia care unit and decreased opioid consumption perioperatively⁷.

We studied 60 randomly selected patients who were undergoing ankle and foot surgeries and administered ultrasonography guided popliteal nerve block. We monitored them closely and analyzed the data obtained.

Patient characteristics:

In our study, ASA grade I/II/III patients were enrolled (table 1).

It is comparable to study of Van Geffen GJ, van den Broek E, Braak GJ, Giele JL, Giele MJ, Schaffer GJ (2009)⁴⁵ who studied the effect of Ultrasound-Guided Popliteal Sciatic Block with a Single Injection at the Sciatic Division.

It is also comparable to Malouf D, Liu SS, Movahedi R, Goytizolo E, Memtsoudis SG, et al. (2012)²³ who studied Nerve stimulator versus ultrasound guidance for placement of popliteal catheters for foot and ankle surgery.

TECHNIQUE OF BLOCKAGE:

We have used ultrasound as a tool to give popliteal nerve block.

Perlas A, Brull R, Chan VW, et al. (2008)³¹, Mariano ER, Cheng GS, et al. (2009)²⁵, Van Geffen GJ, et al (2009)⁴⁵ and Gelfand HJ, Ouanes JP, Lesley MR, Ko PS, et al. (2011)¹⁴ all concluded that when compared to neurostimulation or other techniques, ultrasound has a higher success rate, faster onset, a less painful application, faster progression of sensory motor block, all without an increase in block procedure time or complications.

Malouf D, Liu SS, Movahedi R, Goytizolo E, Memtsoudis SG, et al. (2012)²³ and Dufour E, Quennesson P, Van Robais AL, Ledon F, Laloë PA, et al. (2008)¹² concluded that with ultrasonography, less anesthetic is required without any compromise in efficacy.

• **VOLUME OF LOCAL ANAESTHETIC SOLUTION USED:**

- In our study, we have used 10ml of lignocaine (1.5%) and 10ml Bupivacaine (0.5%) and total volume of 20ml.

It is comparable to that suggested by, Southerland JT, Boberg JS, Downey MS, Nakra A (2009)⁴¹, who have suggested to use 20-30 cc of local anaesthetic which includes injection bupivacaine (0.5%) and injection lignocaine (1.5%). But it is more than the study by Techasuk, Wallaya et. al. (2014)⁴³ who concluded that for ultrasound-guided subpar neural (analgesic) popliteal sciatic nerve block, the MEV90 of combined lidocaine 1.0%– bupivacaine 0.25% with epinephrine 5 µg/mL is 13.3 mL (95% confidence interval, 10.2–16.4 mL).

• **TIME TAKEN TO EXECUTE THE BLOCK:** As shown in table2,

In our study, mean time to administer the block was 4.3 ± 1.4 mins,

It was comparable to the study by Hadzic A, Vloka JD¹⁷ and Zetlaoui⁴⁷ who reported the average time to perform a popliteal fossa block was 4.10 minutes, and the motor blockade was complete in all patients within thirty minutes.

• **DURATION OF SENSORY AND MOTOR BLOCKADE (Graph 6 & Graph 7):**

- In our study, mean sensory onset time in our study was 3.1 ± 1.0 mins and mean motor onset time was 7 ± 1.3 mins.

It was less than that studied by Taboda, Muniz M, et al (2003)⁴², who studied the lateral approach to sciatic nerve block in the popliteal fossa and concluded that Onset of complete sensory and motor blockade of the foot was 16.6 +/- 5.1 minutes, 20.1 +/- 5.1 minutes respectively using single injection of 30 mL of ropivacaine 0.75%.

Such a difference was observed probably due to the different drugs used in our study as we have used a mixture of Injection lignocaine (1.5%) 10ml and Injection bupivacaine (0.5%) 10ml.

DURATION OF COMPLETE MOTOR AND SENSORY REGRESSION (Graph 8 &9)

In our study mean time for motor regression was 143.8 ± 13.5 mins, while mean time for sensory regression was 184.8 ± 16.8 mins. The patients' first complaint of pain was at 239.0 ± 22.4 mins. These times were much prolonged than ones encountered in existing studies. This could be attributable to excessive tolerance to pain found in the Indian patients as compared to their western counterparts

Philips (2011)³² performed a retrospective review on treatment of sixteen patients in the emergency department using nerve-stimulator assisted and no stimulating (ultrasound guided) popliteal blocks. Cases included procedures of leg, ankle, and foot such as fracture reduction,

splinting, irrigation, and debridement. In addition to high efficiency, there was a high degree of patient satisfaction. Post procedural anaesthesia lasted 90 to 120 minutes in all cases. It was concluded that this technique offers the advantage of relative cardiopulmonary safety, dense and prolonged analgesia, and maintenance of normal airway reflexes in patients with increased aspiration risk. When comparing two stimulating groups with one non-stimulating group, higher visual analog scores were recorded in the nonstimulating (ultrasound) group at 6-8 hours and 19-23 hours.

HEMODYNAMIC STABILITY:

(Graph 3,4, 5)

Table no 4, 5, 6 and graph no 3, 4, 5 of Pulse rate, SBP, DBP shows stable haemodynamic parameters in each patient.

It is comparable to study by Brown et al. (1992)⁵ who concluded that Intra-operative and postoperative hemodynamic disturbances are minimized as a result of this blockade.

COMPLICATIONS:

In our study, four patients have failure of block. The possible attributing factors could have been improper isolation of the nerve, faulty injection, migration of the needle during drug injection or incorrect identification of the nerve itself.

- Two need sedation and two need general anaesthesia for supplementation to conduct the surgery. No neurological complications or complications regarding the drug adverse effects were noted

Rogobete AF, Bedreag OH et al. (2015)³⁵ and Hajek V, Dessert C, et al. (2012)¹⁸ reported that complications from popliteal nerve blocks are uncommon as the reported rate is 0-10%. The most common complications include incomplete anaesthesia, infection, and neuropraxia. Hajek (18) performed a retrospective study of 157 procedures where a continuous popliteal nerve block was used for hallux valgus surgery. He reported a complication rate of 1.26% in the form of postoperative peripheral neuropathy, complete block failure in 4%, and partial failure in 10%.

Canales MB et. al. (2015)⁷ concluded that popliteal blocks have shown to decrease the amount of perioperative opioid consumption. This can aid in limiting opioid related complications including nausea and vomiting, respiratory depression, constipation, and dependency. Symptoms from general, spinal, or epidural anaesthesia include pain, postoperative nausea and vomiting, urinary retention, as well as respiratory and hemodynamic instability. These complications were not noted in our study as we have used ultrasound guided local anaesthetic agent. Many of these issues can be circumvented with the popliteal sciatic nerve block.

CONCLUSION:

Ultrasonography guided popliteal nerve block is an effective and successful alternative technique to provide perioperative sensory and motor blockage with less volume of LA, faster onset with virtue of post-operative analgesia with minimum adverse effects even in high-risk patients undergoing various ankle and foot surgeries.

Conflict of Interest: Nil

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